

AVAILABILITY AND USE OF ICT IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES FOR EDUCATIONAL GROWTH AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE OF NIGERIA- KOREA FRIENDSHIP INSTITUTE OF VOCATIONAL AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY LIBRARY, LOKOJA

Michael Kolade Adebisi(CLN)

Institute Librarian, Nigeria-
Korea Friendship Institute of Vocational and
Advanced Technology Library (NKFI) - Lokoja
adebisikolademichael69@gmail.com

Femi Simon Ehonyotan(CLN)

Department of Library and Information Science,
School of Management Studies (SMS)
Kogi State Polytechnic- Lokoja
Fehonyotan@yahoo.com

Abstract

This research explored Availability and Use of ICT in Academic Libraries for Education growth and National development, Evidence of Nigeria- Korea Friendship Institute of Vocational and Advanced Technology Library, Lokoja. It also x-rays the potential of ICT on the services of academic libraries if it can enhance education growth and National development. Literatures of scholars and authors in the field were reviewed, and Descriptive Survey method was employed, In order to achieve the purpose and objectives of this study, questionnaire was designed to elicit information from the respondents. The sample size for the study was twenty (20) of library staff (professional=8 and para-professional=12) which is 20 (100%) of the total population. Critical analysis of the study was carried out using four point Likert rating and the major findings revealed that ICT were available in Nigeria- Korea Friendship Institute of Vocational and Advanced Technology Library, Lokoja; it's very effective in enhancing library services, but the challenges facing ICT processes in academic libraries makes it a discouraging process. Therefore, the study recommended that adequate funds should be provided on a regular basis to make ICT library resources available and effective in use. In addition, Library staff should be trained on the

utilization of these digitized resources to improve their level of ICT literacy and Management of NKFI library should encourage the constant training of such Library staff so as to be kept abreast of changes in the digital world.

Keywords: *Information, Information and Communication Technology, Academic Libraries, Educational growth, National development*

Introduction

Information Communication Technology (ICT) has remained a catalyst in the issue of National development; it is a resource that serves as vital tool in the easy transfer of information or knowledge with a device or machine to people who need and use it across all sectors in any nations, especially in Nigeria- Korea Friendship Institute Vocational and Advanced Technology Library, Lokoja and education sector at large.

Nigeria- Korea Friendship Institute Vocational and Advanced Technology Library, Lokoja was established within the heart of the institute to serve the entire communities on their various programs such like automobile, electrical- electronics, welding and fabrication, computer engineering, and networking and security services in the year 2014, alongside when the institute was established. On this note the library is expected to make ICT resources available for the programs to harness educational growth and development. It is imperative that availability of ICT application in NKFI would go long ways in satisfying the information need of students and scholar of the institute hence the citizenry in Nigeria. If education must grow, libraries as the hub of educational system must be revived in the area of Information

Communication Technology. ICT helps the academic librarians and users to enable them access, recover, save, organize, manipulate, exhibit and disseminate information. Library routines, operations and or services that were initially performed manually are now being converted to computerization which provides better and faster services to the end users of the library. On assumption, it is observed that the availability of ICT infrastructures in most academic Libraries is grossly inadequate and has not been effective operationally. This on assumption has been a challenge to the potential on routines of Libraries and in turn has affected the NKFI library hence educational development. Be that as it may, the Government as the sole player need to improve education which will effectively sustain National development, however it has not been given ICT priority attention in academic Libraries in Nigeria, despite that ICT is the major key individual access to information quickly that will make educational attainment a success. Government should make sure ICTs infrastructures be adequately provided, re-invigorated towards knowledge acquisition and research. Why is it that the educational level is in shuffle state, it is because ICTs have not been applying to library services properly, or is it that information need are not easily and efficiently disseminated to the library users as a result of non-availability of ICT, which would not help staffs performing their job creditably? But the fact remains that if ICTs potentials

are harnessing properly into the administration of academic libraries, the teaching and learning effectiveness will be made possible and its multiplier effect is educational growth and hence National development. Be that as it may, the worrisome question here is the fact that Information Communication Technologies and its accessories were almost not available or inadequate and not useable in some academic libraries which need to be improved, be available and useable if our educational and national economic must be developed. It is on this note that the researchers want to assess NKFI- library if there are availability and or usability of ICT in their library at this digital age.

Statement of the Research Problem

The effective use of Information and Communication technologies (ICTs) in academic libraries is crucial for providing access to a vast array of digital resources, enhancing research capabilities, and supporting academic excellence. However, many academic libraries in Nigeria face significant challenges in providing adequate ICT infrastructure and services to support teaching, learning, and research. The Nigeria- Korea Friendship Institute of Vocational and Advanced Technology Library, Lokoja as a leading institution in Vocational and Advanced Technologies requires a well-equip library that leverages ICTs to provides access to digital resources, facilitate research, and support student learning outcomes. Availability and use of ICTs in the Nigeria-Korea Friendship Institute's library (NKFI) may be hindered by several factors, including inadequate infrastructure, limited access to digital resources, insufficient training for librarians and inadequate funding. Be that as it may, it is on assumption that current available ICT resources are inadequate for addressing the long term needs of NKFI Library users, and a sustainable future. I t is on this note that this study aims to investigate the availability and use of ICTs with a view to identify the challenges and opportunities for improving ICT-based services in the library. Libraries as the hub of educational system must be revived in the area of Information Communication Technology of any library, this is because ICT helps the academic librarians and users to enable them access, recover, save, organize, manipulate, exhibit and disseminate information.

Research Questions

To what extent are the ICTs and its Accessories available and usable in NKFI library Lokoja?

1. To what extent are the adequacies of ICT in NKFI academic library Lokoja?
2. To what extent are the impacts of ICT in NKFI Academic Library to ease and support the Library services in the teaching, learning and research?
3. What are the current states of ICT in NKFI library Lokoja?
4. What are the challenges of ICT in library to help in education growth and National development?

Significant of the Study

This study will provide valuable insights into the availability and use of ICTs in the Nigeria-Korea friendship Institute of Vocational and Advanced Technologies Library, Lokoja. The findings will be useful for Librarians, policy makers, the management and

other stakeholders in identifying areas for improvement and developing strategies for enhancing ICT-based services in the library. Also This research work will help in the consolidating and strengthening the provision of information resources in academic Libraries, it will help to facilitate institutional provision of e-resources, data and information services; the findings of this research will equally help the government to plan and take useful decision on the provision of information and ICT resources that will eradicate challenges and improving standard of education through Library services. above all, the study will be of important to the NKFI personnel and students; this is because the adequate information and current news will be made possible to help them in discharging their duties, and to have current and regular information for teaching and learning.

Literature review

This section review relevant literatures and contributors to the topic for better understanding of the topical issues on ICT resources in academic libraries.

Information

Information is a vital resource; this is because it plays a key role in every sphere of life. Omoniwa & Adebisi (2017) sees information as the core of success to individuals, corporate bodies and business enterprises. Consequently, information may be defined as a fact or set of facts that can influence a person's response in a given situation. According to Mahmud (2012) information is facts and opinion provided and received during the course of daily life. In another related view, He further observed that information is an order sequence or symbol, message and it is said to be anything that adds to an existing knowledge. Invariably information can be described as teaching, enlightenment and to create awareness in an environment or society. Adebisi, M. K., Olorunlagbara, V.B & Kutu, J.A (2023) asserted that information is popularly used to create awareness, sensitizing and teaching people about issues and matters arising and affecting their individual lives. Nothing renews the minds like information; it enlarges the capacity of the mind and enhances qualitative and effective reasoning.

This information is perceived to be facts, intelligence, data, news or knowledge necessary for decision making. Information is power and when they are adequately provided and use, it is relevant and valued to the society. The countries that have the capacity to acquire or generate and manage information use it to improve their societal-economic status and advance ahead of other nations that do not have such capacity.

Considering the importance of Information, Afolabi & Abidoye (2018) thus argued that:

-

- 1.Information is a strategic resource or critical tool to all levels and it has both unique and common attributes
- 2.In order to exploit information in its maximum level, it must be managed.
- 3.Information is an instrument of power
- 4.Information has both benefit and cost

5.Information is in congruent with other resources - human, physical, financial and technological infrastructures.

Ways by which information can be transferred/ Disseminated to users in academic libraries

Source: Adapted from Ehonyotan, F.S & Adebisi, M.K (2022)

Information can be generated and disseminated through radio, television, newspapers and some social media such like tweeters, what's up app; Face book, Google, hotspot, Instagram, video message, voice mail across to people as illustrated above. Some of these channels are used and many others to interact, contact, research and to teach or enlightened. This Information is considered as the fifth needs and of man ranking after air, water, food and shelter it is also the fifth factors of production aside from Capital, Land, Labor and Entrepreneur respectively.

Information and Communication Technology

Afolabi & Abidoye (2018) defined ICT as compound words that connote Information and communication Technology facilitating transfer of information from point to another. They further argued that Information and communication Technology (ICT) has demonstrated its impact on the library resources, systems, services and operations. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has also integrated the world and changed the entire global education scenario. According to Adebisi (2016)

and Ochai (2007), ICT tools and its techniques enhanced teaching, learning, scientific research and governance in the Academic institution. For ICT, we need infrastructure, internet connectivity, and digital equipment, secure platform, digitally competent and confident educator. While Hussain (2018) emphasized that the essence of ICT is in its power to help individuals and societies achieve greater access to knowledge and ideas for the benefit of humanity. Singh (2018) have identified the benefits of ICT in library operations to include; provision of speedy accurate and easy access to information; provision of remote access to users; provision of up-to-date information; permanent storage of information; saves time as well as generating fund and enhancement of research, enhanced accessibility to information from all over the world through the internet, wide range information materials that are made available in different formats thereby increasing accessibility to information (Adewoyin, 2017). This corresponds with the

assertion of Lubanga & Mumba (2021) and Mittal (2017) that ICT allows easy integration of various library activities, increases efficiency in acquisition, cataloguing, classification, information retrieval and dissemination. Odunfuwa (2006) observed that the result of harnessing ICT in academic library operation is that the library staff will have more energy and time which can be used to attending to more library users and perform more professional duties. Partel & Partel (2018) noted that with the use of ICT, time of the user will be saved thereby enhancing and increasing patronage of the library services to help the informed society road map to national development. The question here in this work is that, are these ICT and its accessories available and use in today's academic institution to support educational glory? This is subject to respondents' view in academic libraries.

Academic Libraries

Academic Libraries according to Mbashir, Ehonyotan, Audu, & Adebisi (2013) are those libraries attached with universities, Polytechnics and colleges of Education for the purpose of information provisions. Library established to ensure quality and sustainable education by promoting literacy. The academic library is the nerve centre or the hub around which scholarship revolves, to Deepak (2018) it is an indispensable instrument for intellectual development as blood is essential to human body and the survival of all living organism. In his own observation, Ajie (2019) observed that academic libraries have for centuries played critically important roles in supporting research in all subjects and disciplines within their host universities or colleges. While Ratheeswari (2018) also posits that the library stands in the same relationship to the society as the memory of an individual by making information available and accessible to its users for teaching and independent study. The main purpose of an academic library as stated by Afolabi & Abidoye (2018) is to support the objectives of an academic environment in the areas of learning, teaching, research, and service. In their own contributions, Ajibero (2013) and Idowu (2011) discussed the challenges of academic libraries that ICT in academic libraries are not sometimes adequate physically or electronically for users to satisfy vary degrees, and to achieve this several measures have been put in place such as the adoption of ICT accessories, E-learning and E-teaching.

Educational Growth and Academic Library

Education is the process of learning in order to develop physically, socially, emotionally, intellectually and economically (FME, 2010). An educated person is not only literate but has also developed his or her mental and reasoning power and is knowledgeable, which is the primary aim of Academic Libraries (Idowu, 2011). The main purpose of education is to draw out any desirable change in the behaviour of the learners through the growth and development of the physical, mental and spiritual capabilities to enable him or her to have a useful, enjoyable and productive life in the society, workplace and home (Adebisi, Ehoniyotan & Adebisi, 2023; NPE, 1992). Ratheeswari (2018) argued that education is relevance and its quality coexist imperatively expanding the educational opportunities globally using ICTs and internet infrastructures, it is enabling tools for education change and transformation, this is because through ICT effectiveness in the library, it helps to expand and gain access to education strengthening the importance of education and increasingly raised education quality making teaching and learning into an active process connected to real life (Adebisi & Ehoniyotan, 2019).

National Development and the Role of Library in Nigeria

The idea of National Development is born out of the need for every member of a given society to actively participate in the upliftment of such a society. National Development concept therefore entails the situation whereby opportunities are opened to every member of the society to participate actively in the realization of the society goals and objectives. (Adebisi, Olorunlagbara, & Kutu, 2023) Social indicators of proper national development includes such factors like higher per capital income earning, socio – political as well as economic independent etc in a society where the majority wallows in the abject poverty with high rate of unemployment, low socio – economic level etc is not a development (Ajie, 2019). The challenge is enormous for the library to operate and function in such society. This is the situation as we have with us today in Nigeria which ultimately caused for a real examination of the role of library and information centre in Nigeria (Waljat, 2018). National Development ought to begin at the person to person library and information service level. Therefore, library and information leads to enhance individual development with the adequate services been provided. Its contribution to National Development objectives is sure to glaring. This library and information center can do by ensuring that their stock of collections in both printed and non – printed formats are well as collective dreams and aspirations of the society where they are found. Regular and continuous actual needs of its community information likewise, need proper stocking of the library and information centers with relevant materials for National Development.

Availability and Use of Ict in Academic Libraries

The availability and use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has great potential in improving the quality of education throughout the country (Ehoniyotan, Adebisi & Samuel, 2023). They further discussed that ICT involves the utilization of technological tools that can support Lecturers to be innovative and effective in teaching while allowing students to learn at their own pace. The pace of change brought

about by new information technologies, and it has affected on the way people live, work and play worldwide (Alegbeleye, 2009). Purnik (2022) discovered that computer and ICT access is paramount to students and is also far more pertinent than physical book. According to Adebisi, Olorunlagbara & Kutu, (2023) ICT in Academic Libraries and its application to library services need to be automated, harnessed to help in promoting educational development that will in turn have positive impact on National development at large. The development of ICT enables learners to learn more effectively, efficiently, flexibly and comfortably. However, the presence of ICTs promoter touched virtually all dimensions of higher education and today there are many different types in which ICT has been visualize as a medium for teaching and learning which included computer assisted learning, web-learning, computer classes, distance education learning, virtual learning, digital training etc, In almost all the Colleges, Polytechnic and Universities have started using computer and ICT as means of transfer information through machine and accessories. ICT has been organized in different ways to ensure acquisition of knowledge and it is important to monitor learning process and to make it more efficient, available and accepted as potentials of ICT considering its positive effect on teaching and learning during 21st century (Afolabi & Abidoye, 2018).

Impact and Benefit of availability and use of ICT Resources

Countries across the world are using ICT in facilitating information, dissemination and communication in all areas of education and training. Generally, it has been observed that using ICT resources by students is imperative, the use of computer and ICTs are usually more of benefits to support discussion, interaction and feedback, and effectively motivate students, making the classes more dynamic and interesting and renew Lecturers' enthusiasm as they learn new skills and techniques and its benefits in education are to enable greater learner autonomy, enable tasks to be tailored to suit individual skills, enable students to demonstrate achievement in ways which might not be possible with traditional methods, it also unlocks hidden potential for those with communication problems (Deepak, 2018; Omoniwa & Adebisi, 2017). Accordingly, one of the major negative impacts of ICT in education is ethical rot. These include access to inappropriate materials; Stealing of software or the use of unlicensed/ pirated software, It is exceedingly easy to do "cut and paste" without referencing the source and without paying attention to copyright laws. Plagiarism has increased resulting in decline of educational standard. The students highly dependent on ICT lose their analytical skill, mathematical skill and judgment skills (Deepak, 2018; Omoniwa & Adebisi, 2017).

Challenges Facing ICT in Academic Libraries

Some challenges facing ICT especially in Academic libraries are: -Inadequate of ICT facilities and ICT skills, Lack of ICT policies, Erratic power supply, Lack of technical IT knowledge staff, Constant change of software and hardware, Violation of Copyright and intellectual property policy, Limited financial resources, Poor maintenance of ICT equ

ipment, Insufficient and width,

Insufficient data usage, Problems of service distribution, Environmental factors, Inadequate funds, Poor ICTs maintenance etc.

Information Communication Technology (ICT) as a Tools

There are various available tools which can be utilized for the knowledge creation and dissemination in the modern world, sometimes called emerging technologies. Tools which include Interactive Smart Board, Computer, Projector, Television, Video conference, Wi-Fi/LAN, Smart classrooms, e-library, College website, Personal ICT resources like mobile/tablet, PC/ laptop, Net connectivity, Big Data, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT), Web based tools (Web 2.0/3.0) enable student registration, track learner progress, record test scores and indicate course completion (Rathna & Divyananda, 2018). It enables parents to review the students' performance online, Plagiarism detection system is available to check of plagiarism of text (Ehoniyan, Adebisi & Samuel, 2023). Institutional Repository, RFID Technology, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Book Delivery, Drone and Library Tracker and many others that are captured Tablets loaded with math apps and e-text book used to access real time information, receive instruction, record measurements and conduct research (Purnik, 2022). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming more and more prevalent in everyday life. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the study of mental capacities using computational models in this age of science and technology, To Neogi & Partap (2018) according to Singh (2018), Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) is the computerized version of library catalogues. It provides access to the catalogues of a library on the local intranet, extranet allows users to access their personal and official files from any computer with internet access (Afolabi & Abidoye, 2018, Karimi, 2014). All these emanated from ICT shortly after traditional library and it has helped education sector to promote growth and development in Nigeria libraries.

Research Methodology

The research employed descriptive survey method to evaluate quantitatively on information communication technology (ICT) and its resources in the Academic libraries of the NKFI Lokoja. The entire librarians 20 (100%) participated in the study. The method is also going to involve observations, questionnaire using four point Likert rating to assess the impact, availability and usability of ICT in academic libraries, other relevant journals, and books relating to the research work were used to draw inferences.

Method of Data Analysis and Discussion

In this research, data analysis would be computed using statistical packages for the data collected. Data were analyzed using four point Likert rating to find the mean statistics of the data at a decision criterion of 2.5 above accepted and 2.5 below rejected.

Note: -Response Interpretation

SA=Strongly Agree, A= Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree/

VHE=Very High Extent, HE=High Extent, LE=Low Extent, VLE=Very Low Extent/

HA = Highly Adequate, A= Adequate, LA=Low Adequate, NA= Not Adequate.

Discussion of result

Below are the tables and analysis of data collected in Likert point rating to calculate the result drawn from the respondents.

Research Q1)To what extent are the ICT and its Accessories available and usable in NKFI library Lokoja?

R Q	DESCRIPTION OF ITEMS	N	V H E	H E	L E	V L E	ME AN	RAT ING	RAN KING
Q I	1) To what extent are the ICT and its Accessories available and usable in NKFI library Lokoja?	20	10	10	0	0	3.5	A	2 nd

Sources: Field Survey 2024.

From the table above, respondents' view shows that ICT and its Accessories (new emerging ICT resources) are available and usable in Academic library of NKFI Lokoja with a Mean Statistics of (3.5), however, the mean statistics of the data at a decision criterion of 3.5 above is accepted. It is observed that the need to still improve on the availability and usability of the NKFI Academic Library can be made possible. According to Ehonyotan, Adebisi & Samuel, (2023) and Rathna & Divyananda, (2018) agreed that there are various available tools which can be utilized for the knowledge creation and dissemination in the modern world, sometimes called emerging technologies. Tools which include Interactive Smart Board, Computer, Projector, Television, Video conference, Wi-Fi/LAN, Smart classrooms, e-library, College website, Personal ICT resources like mobile/tablet, PC/ laptop, Net connectivity, Big Data, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT) Web based tools (Web 2.0/3.0) etc.

Research Q2) To what extent are the adequacies of ICT in NKFI academic library Lokoja?

Q2	DESCRIPTION OF ITEMS	N	HA	A	LA	NA	MEAN	RATING	RANKING
	2) To what extent are the adequacies of ICT in NKFI academic library Lokoja?	20	2	4	10	4	2.2	R	5 th

Sources: Field Survey 2024.

The analysis from research question 2 in the table above, revealed that ICT resources are inadequate in NKFI Academic library with Likert point rating of (2.2) which is below 2.49 rejected; it then means the ICT resources are not enough for the accredited programs such as Automobile, Electrical/electronics, Computer engineering, Welding and Fabrication, Networking and Security Services.

Deepak (2018), Omoniwa & Adebisi (2017) support this assertion that one of the major negative impacts of ICT in education is its ethical rot, access to inappropriate materials; Inadequate of ICT facilities and ICT infrastructures, Insufficient bandwidth, and data usage, However, they all noted that many academic libraries in Nigeria face significant challenges in providing adequate ICT infrastructure and services to support teaching, learning, and research. Also Ajibero (2013) and Idowu (2011) observed that ICT in academic libraries are not sometimes adequate physically or electronically for users to satisfy their varying degrees. It was generally observed that Availability and use of ICTs in the Nigeria-Korea Friendship Institute’s library (NKFI) may be hindered by inadequate infrastructure, limited access to digital resources. Be that as it may, current available ICT resources are inadequate for addressing the long term needs of NKFI Library users, and a sustainable future.

Research Q3) To what extent are the impacts of ICT in NKFI Academic Library to ease the Library services?

Q3	DESCRIPTION OF ITEMS	N	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	MEAN	RATING	RANKING
	3) To what extent are the impacts of ICT in NKFI Academic Library to ease the Library services?	20	6	8	4	1	2.9	A	4

Sources: Field Survey 2024.

Respondents’ view on the impacts of ICT to ease Library services, the analysis above shows that ICT resources of the NKFI academic library helps library work to be done easily compare with traditional services of the library that was slow, waste time and very laborious in the operation of the library. It was shown that activities are very fast, current and interesting with accepted point of (2.9) reference to the research question 3 in the table above.

Alegbeleye (2009), Purnik (2022) discovered that computer and ICT access is paramount to students and is also far more pertinent than physical book. According to Ehoniyan, Adebisi & Samuel (2023) noted and said that ICT involves the utilization of technological tools that can support Lecturers to be innovative and effective in teaching while allowing students to learn at their own pace. ICT enables learners to learn more effectively, efficiently, flexibly and comfortably and it also serves as a medium for teaching and learning which included computer assisted learning, web-learning etc.

Research Q4) what are the current states of ICT in NKFI library Lokoja in terms Relevat, Effectiveness, and efficiency etc

Q4	DESCRIPTION OF ITEMS	N	SA	A	D	S D	MEAN	RATING	RANKING
	4) What are the current states of ICT in NKFI library Lokoja? ICT and its e- resources of the NKFI academic library are current in use, relevant, efficiently and effectively for the purpose of promoting Educational growth for National Development.	20	14	4	2	0	3.6	A	1st

Sources: Field Survey 2024.

The current state of the ICT and its e- resources of the NKFI academic library are current in use, relevant, efficiently and effectively for the purpose of promoting Educational growth for National Development, this was rated with four point Likert rating ranked with respondents of Mean Statistics (3.6) and making use of ICT in library will help facilitating teaching and learning and easily promote reading culture, hence National development. According to Afolabi & Abidoye (2018) agreed that ICT is to support the objectives of an academic environment in the areas of learning, teaching, research, and service. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has remained a catalyst in the issue of National development; it is a resource that serves as vital tool in the easy transfer of information or knowledge with a device or machine to people who need and use it across all sectors in any nations. In some cases, they observed that ICT in most academic Libraries is grossly inadequate and has not been effective operationally and most materials are not relevant. Adebisi, Olorunlagbara & Kutu, (2023) disagreed with this statement that ICT in Academic Libraries and its application to library services need to be automated, harnessed to help in promoting educational development that will in turn have positive impact on National development at large. The development of ICT enables learners to learn more effectively, efficiently and comfortably.

Research Q5) what are the Challenges of ICT in library to help for education growth and National Development?

Q	DESCRIPTION OF ITEMS	N	SA	A	D	S D	ME AN	RAT ING	RAN KING
5	5) What are the challenges of ICT in library to help in education growth and National development?								
	Major challenges of the ICT are Fund, Erratic power supply, Lack of technical IT knowledge staff, Constant change of software and hardware, Inadequate of ICT facilities.	20	10	8	2	0	3.4	A	3rd

Sources: Field Survey 2024.

Major challenges of the ICT according to Respondents' view and the analysis computed on the table above, it was shown that Fund, Erratic power supply, ICT facilities are considered the major problems with the mean statistics of (3.4). It was observed that there are ways to harness these problems facing the Academic libraries mention above by equipping and funds the functional areas of the libraries e,g cataloguing, classification, personnel policies and others modern equipment and infrastructures that are inadequate or non- available, this is in line with the viewers suggestions. But in the same view, Purnik (2022) agreed and outline some of the above factors as challenges to ICT in academic Libraries.

Summary of findings

The study and result can be summarized as follows that

- 1) ICT and its Accessories (new emerging ICT resources) are available and usable in Academic library of NKFI Lokoja with a Mean Statistics of (3.5)
- 2) ICT resources are inadequate in NKFI Academic library with Likert point rating of (2.2) rejected
- 3) The impacts of ICT in the library is to ease Library services, ICT resources of the NKFI academic library helps library work to be done easily compare with traditional services of the library that was slow, time wasted, and very laborious in the operation of the library with accepted point of (2.9)
- 4) The current state of the ICT and its e- resources of the NKFI academic library are current in use, relevant, efficiently and effectively for the purpose of promoting Educational growth for National development, with Mean Statistics of (3.6)
- 5) Major challenges of the ICT are Fund, Erratic power supply, Lack of technical IT knowledge staff, Constant change of software and hardware, Inadequate of ICT facilities are considered the major problems with the mean statistics of (3.4).

However, the result found in this study can be generalized in any academic libraries, although the challenges may be slightly different. Be that as it may, academic Libraries need to be harnessed because of inadequacy and non-availability of e-resources and Information Communication Technologies.

Conclusion

The application of ICT is unavoidable for the sustainable development of the educational establishment; the NKFI institution must focus on developing ICT infrastructures, although it requires high investment. ICT will support educational community in various ways; accessibility and affordability of ICT tools are major concern for the lecturers, students and scholars of any country who are not that much technology confidence. It also helps in supervising and Vetting of students, thesis and dissertation at graduation, grammar software, webinar software packages are relevant in the vetting and corrections of students, lecturers' seminar presentation as well. Availability and utilizing of ICT Facilities and infrastructures has made remarkable on road to the educational, economic, religious cultural, legal and social life of Nations particularly that of the developing countries like Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations are thus made: -

- Adequate funds should be provided on a regular basis to maintain the ICT library resources and their media available, and useable.
- Adequate technology infrastructures should be provided for all the programs in the NKFI
- Library staff should be trained on the utilization of these digitized resources to improve their level of ICT literacy and also management of academic libraries should encourage the constant training of such library staff so as to be kept abreast of changes in the digital world.
- ICT should be made available; in all academic libraries such like Universities, Polytechnic, and Colleges of education to promote educational development in turn uphold National development.

References

Adebisi, M.K (2016). *Advanced Library Automation*. Lokoja: JHL press.

Adebisi, M.K (2011). *Introduction to Internet and Virtual Library*. Lokoja: JHL Ltd.

Adebisi, M. K., Olorunlagbara, V.B & Kutu, J.A (2023). *Digital Library Services and Sustainable National Development in Nigeria Being a paper presented to the School of Management Studies, Kogi State polytechnic Lokoja on the theme Digital Economy in Nigeria towards genuine Inclusivity for Sustainable National Development 25th -27th July, 2023. Hall A, Main Campus – Lokoja.*

Afolabi, A.F & Abidoye J.A (2018). *The Integration of Information Technology in Library Operations towards Effective Library Services. Proceeding of 1st International Technology, Education and Environment Conference at African Society for Scientific Research (ASSR)*. Accessed on 20 May 2023.

Ajie, I. (2019). *Information Service Provision by Librarians in the Era of Globalization. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved 21/05/ 2024 from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2517>.

Alegbeleye, G.O. (2009). *Avoiding technological quicksand: Coming to grips with the preservation of digital information in Nigeria*. A Paper presented at the 47th National Conference and Annual General Meeting of the Nigerian Library Association. July 26 - 31, 2009.

- Adewoyin, O.O (2017) ICT Skills, Social Media Use and Service delivery by Librarian in Federal University in South-West, Nigeria (Unpublished Master's dissertation) Department of Information Resources & Management: School of Management, Babcock University Ilishan- Remo, Ogun State Nigeria. Accessed on 2nd May, 2023.
- Deepak, P. (2018). Role of ICT on Universities Administrative Service and Management. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 1(1), 5-11.
- Ehoniyyotan, F.S & Adebisi, M.K (2022). Consolidate Military Libraries with Strategic Information Resources for National Security in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Multi-disciplinary Research (IJAMR)*. 9 (2), 159-171
- Ehoniyyotan, F. S., Adebisi, M.K & Adebisi V.O (2023). Re-invigorating Internet of Things for Quality Library Services in Academic Libraries towards Sustainable Education Development Being a paper presented at the School of Applied Sciences, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja, on 5th Annual National Conference, Workshop and Exhibition, Thursday 6th- 8th June, 2023.
- Ehoniyyotan, F. S., Adebisi, M.K & Samuel, M. R (2023). Emerging Technologies for Library Services towards Sustainable Environmental Development. Being a paper presented at the School of Applied Sciences, Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja, on 5th Annual National Conference, Workshop and Exhibition, Thursday 6th- 8th June, 2023.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2010) Six Point Agencies of the Federal Ministry of Education. Abuja; FME
- Federal Ministry of Science and Technology (2001) Nigeria National policy for Information Technology (IT). Abuja.
- Funmilayo, R. and Ayo, O. (2020). Global trends and emerging technologies in libraries and information Science. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 3835. Retrieved on 5/6/2024 from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/3835>
- Hussain, A. H. (2018). Awareness of Web 2.0 Technology in the Academic Libraries: An Islamabad Perspective *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved 5/6/2024 from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1945>
- Idowu, O.A. (2011). Effective Library services in the college. A paper delivered at the 1st Library workshop at Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. Access date: 20/06/2024.

- Karimi, H. A. (2014). Big data: techniques and technologies in geoinformatics. New York: Taylor and Francis Group.
- Lubanga, S. & Mumba, J. (2021). Research and Development (R&D), Creativity and Innovation in Academic Libraries in Malawi: A Way to rethink library development in the 21st Century Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3867430>
- Mahmud, M. M (2012). Information a tool for National Development. *Middle Belt Journal of Library and Information Science*. 10(1), 129-145.
- Mbashir, A. L; Ehoniyan, F.S; Audu, O.O.M & Adebisi, M.K (2010). General Library Studies I. Lokoja: JHL Prints.Ltd.
- Mittal, A. (2017). Emerging technologies and their impact on the libraries. *Indian Journal of Science and technology*. 10 31). DOI: 10.17485/ijst/2017/v10i31/113915
- National Policy on Education (1992) as Revised; Abuja: NPE
- Neogi, P & Partap, B. (2019). Application of emerging technologies in libraries: An overview. Retrieved from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/334670378>
- Ochai, G. (2007). Information and Communication Technologies at a glance. Nsukka: Excellent Press.
- Odunfuwa, S (2006). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a research tool in libraries *Nigerbiblios*, 17(1 & 2): 100-105.
- Oghenetega, L. U., Umeji, E. C. & Obue, C. N. (2014). Challenges Associated with the Use of ICT Facilities in Public Library of Nigeria. *Developing Country Studies*, 4 (22): 1-5 <https://bit.ly/3DYp2rB>
- Omoniwa, M.A & Adebisi, M.K (2017). Information as a Critical Resource in the Implementation National Development Programs. *Lokoja Journal of Management and Technology*. 5(1) 67-78.
- Patel, U. & Patel, S. (2018). Use of Social Media Networking in Libraries. *Proceedings of International Conference on Internet of Things and Current Trends in Libraries* 64-67
- Purnik, A. (2022). The Internet of Things Serving Libraries. International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions serving-libraries. Retrieved from <https://www.ifla.org/g/libraries-for-children-an-ya/the-internet-of-things->

- Ratheeswari, K. (2018). Information Communication Technology in Education. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*. S45-S47.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.21839/jaar.2018.v3SI.169>.
- Rathna, P.& Divyananda, K. (2018). Emerging technology skills among library professionals of Autonomous College Libraries in Karnataka. *Indian Journal of Information Source and Service*, 8, (2).
- Singh, R. (2018). Future of libraries by innovation and technologies: Marching beyond libraries. New Delhi: ND, Overseas Press India, 113-121.
- Waljat, N. (2018). Radio frequency identification device. Retrieved from <https://www.waljatcollege.edu.com/downloads.php>